

Technology Converge is Reshaping the 6G Access Network Architecture but are Our Infrastructures Ready to Cope?

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Abstract— The goal of 6G is to further advance the quality of experience in human-human communications while it transforms the I4.0 landscape by integrating a diverse set of technologies, services, and applications. To achieve this goal, there are rapid convergence steps between wireline and wireless technologies toward a unified transportation platform, something that prompts architectural modifications. Intelligence is now distributed closer to end-users, with Far-Edge nodes becoming essential. However, these nodes must balance performance and affordability for operators. Moreover, the converged wireline and wireless technologies must consider the scarcity of fiber in the last-mile. In this work we contribute to the debate of parallel, decoupled fiber infrastructures vs. a single passive PtMP connectivity scheme under the framework of fiber scarcity and for residential users with multi-Gb/s line-rates while small-cells exploit mmWave technology with > 100 MHz RF bandwidth. Our analysis is based on the information supplied by operators regarding the practical constraints and limitation arising from real-life deployments and it is based on realistic geospatial data. We conclude that fiber utilization becomes prohibitively high under both alternatives when low-cost, grey interfaces are employed, and the deployments become viable in terms of fiber utilization only when, colored interfaces and WDM is introduced. Furthermore, this work contributes to the discussion on the efficacy of next-generation PON technology in accommodating varied capacity requirements without increasing fiber use. The recently announced 25G and 50G TDM PONs are struggling to satisfy connectivity demands within the current fiber deployment frameworks when small cells utilizing high-layer splits (F1) and residential users are served by multi-Gb/s line rates. Beyond this point, when small cells employing low-layer splits are deployed alongside multi-Gb/s line-rate residential users, a shared scheme utilizing PtMP trees and technologies supporting a total capacity of 400G seems to be the next barrier to reach to prevent the depletion of fiber infrastructures. At the end, we report our findings based on the benchmark of alternative 400G solutions against their resource utilization.

Index Terms—6G, Passive Optical Networks, Access Network Architectures

1. INTRODUCTION

The pivotal role of industrial production in our society's welfare is coming again into the spotlight, either because of objective economic development patterns and evolutionary

trends or due to geopolitical tensions and competitions. To serve this dual goal, technology stakeholders are endeavoring to preserve the existing human-to-human communication framework facilitated by advanced consumer devices (PCs, smartphones, tablets, smart gadgets, etc.), while also confronting the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (I4.0) [1]-[4]. The emerging economic epoch anticipates widespread machine-to-machine connectivity wherein tens or even hundreds of billions of assets, such as robotic entities with varying levels of intelligence, are perpetually interconnected and exchange data with minimal or no human intervention.

In the pursuit of these objectives, a progressively broader spectrum of heterogeneous technologies and systems are, firstly, interconnected and then integrated through an overarching control and management framework, ushering in a phase of technological convergence [1]-[4]. This integration serves as a catalyst for the advancement of 6G cloud-based telecommunications infrastructures, which will subsequently establish the foundation for future successive waves of technological convergence across many technology sectors, ultimately leading to a *technological continuum* [1]-[2].

It is worth noting that the currently independent and disparate evolutionary trajectories of many technical fields are already demonstrating signs of convergence due to a "push-pull" impact. For example, as argued in [5], a key feature of the I4.0 smart factory is the flexibility and adaptability of production to respond in real-time to changing customer demands. To do so, not only production and transportation robots should work together, maximizing flexibility and efficiency, but also the robots themselves should be prone to automatic reconfiguration and reprogramming so as to deal with the frequent assignment changes of assembly tasks. Moreover, as demand-driven mass customization transitions from conventional production lines, a converged technological infrastructure is set to realize this leap by amalgamating sensors, software, and networked control with edge-based deep and reinforcement learning into new and powerful production forces [5],[6]. In this context, the development of siloed 6G platforms that exploit ad-hoc connectivity structures, while potentially enabling individual enterprises to penetrate markets faster, imposes substantial costs on the national digital economy due to the number of

concurrent but, still, segregated infrastructures that need to be developed [1].

To overcome these hurdles, a ubiquitous 6G architecture is essential. However, this should be sufficiently generic to promote interoperability and diversity in the implementation plans to support multi-tenancy. In the heart of this trajectory, one finds the convergence between wireline and wireless technologies which are tasked to materialize the diverse set of connectivity needs. However, how this convergence is to be implemented remains a subject of intense discussions.

In particular, although it is clear that wireline networks are an integral part of 6G rather than an external element [7], there are still debates on whether a single or separate transportation infrastructures better serve a diverse set of connectivity requirements [7]-[9].

The wireline-wireless convergence makes it necessary to rethink certain assumptions being made during the time the optical and the mobile access networks were completely separate businesses. For example, for over 30 years, Passive Optical Networks (PONs) have been regarded as the technology that allows pushing electronic aggregation and switching technologies deeper into the (Metro) network, decreasing the associated CapEx/OpEx cost due to the use of electronics in the Access segment nodes for (dis)aggregating traffic. Under the quest for a converged infrastructure, we are compelled to re-evaluate the latter assumption. Specifically, there are many arguments suggesting that a Far-Edge node in the close vicinity of end-user is a new reality to which the converged architecture needs to adapt. Due to the pivotal role these nodes play in a converged 6G architecture, the scope of this work is to delineate the integration of Far-Edge nodes into 6G infrastructures and then to quantify how service requirements convert into resource requirements in the Access segment. Furthermore, we analyze how these requirements impact the utilization rate of the existing fiber resources and how prospective optical transportation technologies may alter the corresponding consumption rates.

In section 2 we summarize the main characteristics of the emerging converged architecture in Access and Aggregation segments and we present in detail the rationale behind the pivotal role Far-Edge nodes play in 6G. Last but not least, we present the arguments justifying the emergence of new traffic components in these segments and we provide a potential architectural framework to address them efficiently. Section 3, delineates essential technological aspects of 6G wireline and wireless technologies, with an emphasis given to the practical limitations associated with wireline last-drop implementations. In section 4, we detail our modeling efforts regarding resource allocation and utilization projections, and we give the rationale why advanced optical technologies are needed to confront the challenges of transportation technology convergence. Finally, in Section 5, we are endeavoring to understand the implications future PON technologies may impose on the resources of the Far-Edge node.

2. THE CONVERGED 6G ACCESS NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

The term Far-Edge node is useful when one wishes to declare

that this is a cloud-immersed node i.e. the node is not merely hosting connectivity resources only, but it also supports cloud-based services. However, this is a rather vague definition when the scope is to designate it as a converged telecommunications technology node to be implemented at the footprint on the existing network infrastructure of an Access Central Office (Access CO). Therefore, the term Far-Edge node is typically more appropriate for designating the cloud aspect of a node, whereas Access CO is more appropriate for tackling connectivity challenges.

With this clarification in mind, the two terms are used interchangeably in this work as we further probe the architectural implications this node brings to the functions of a converged network infrastructure.

The next section highlights the features making the Far-Edge node a new reality in a converged 6G Access network.

A. Probing to the Characteristics of the Access CO.

Arguments supporting the necessity of a Far-Edge node can be categorized into three distinctive groups.

I. Due to the Transport Latency Requirements in Next Generation Fronthaul Interfaces (NGFI)

The converged access network architecture must account for the performance limitations and constraints arising from each respective transportation technology. In this specific instance, the limitations stem from 6G NR closed-loop control requirements. In C-RAN 5G/6G deployments, the transport latency is mainly limited by the Hybrid ARQ (HARQ) process for ULLRC applications, which call for very low end-to-end latency performance. As it is specified in [10], the maximum transport distance due to the propagation delay is 10 km, although the typical distance is intended to be below 5 km. The latter value is also implicitly proposed in [11] and is designated in this document to as latency-class *High25* (one-way latency of 25 μ s). It is pointed out that since 5G/6G NR supports multiple frame structures with different HARQ transmission time interval (TTI) configurations, there can be variations in these fronthaul latency requirements. However, in [12], it is contended that these differences are diminished in implementations with bandwidths > 100 MHz RF. A transport network delay budget, and hence physical distance, larger than the one specified above in [10],[11] degrades the mobile network performance. Another important latency class is the High100 requesting a < 100 μ s latency.

II. As a result of Demanding Applications and Industrial Internet Services

In [13], the latency requirements for key ULLRC services are listed. It is emphasized that to get sub-*ms* latency in the access transport system, whether this includes a purely fixed-line transportation network or even more when a wireless technology is also used, transportation latency must be decreased to the greatest extent feasible. In the Table I of [14], a number of industrial applications requiring < 1 ms latency are enumerated. The performance requirements for some of them are so stringent that they can only be met through local control

mechanisms (at a distance of less than 100 m), prohibiting the assignment of this control to a node situated at a remote location.

Additional industrial applications that impose stringent latency requirements associated with their closed-loop control systems include: i) Real-time drone stabilization & collision avoidance. This refers to the dynamic control of autonomous drones to avoid obstacles by machine-learning inference, conducted at the Far-Edge node. This process features a latency of $< 600 \mu\text{s}$; ii) Distributed drone swarm synchronization, where μs -level sync is needed for tight formations, require a loop to be completed within 0.38–0.68 ms; iii) Edge-accelerated motor control of drone’s motor adjustments where the PID (speed control to ensure that a robot’s motors actually turn at the rate you expect them to) is executed at the Edge requires a total loop of 0.24–0.58 ms; iv) mmWave beam tracking for high-speed drones. For drones flying at 30 m/s (108 km/h; e.g., Facebook Aquila) using mmWave (28/60 GHz), the beam updates are carried out at 500–2000 Hz rate, requiring transportation latency $< 200 \mu\text{s}$ to achieve their goal. Similar requirements are obtained for V2X communications exploiting mmWave technology.

A final remark is that, as stated in [5], transmission delays remain an important part of bottlenecks in smart factories and a considerable fraction of the overall end-to-end (E2E) delay budget. The researchers in [15] propose a wireless isochronous real-time system for I4.0 with a latency of 100 μs , utilizing ultra-wideband wireless technology. To achieve this performance goal of less than 100 μs latency in the context of an I4.0 application having many additional latency sources, the geographic distance between the RU and DU/CU elements plays a key role. In fact, the proliferation of services requiring a control-loop in the sub-*ms* range will be greatly enhanced, and the corresponding performance will be improved by *minimizing* the physical transportation length between the sensor/gateway and the location edge processing takes place. All objectives enumerated in this subsection are accomplished by the architecture outlined in section 2.B.

III. As a result of Architectural Quests for lower CapEx/OpEx

The works [16],[17] are showcasing considerable CapEx/OpEx savings when such Far-Edge node (identified as an Active Remote Node -ARN in these publications) aggregates the traffic from heterogeneous last-drop technologies and it optically bypass Edge/Metro nodes in the context of optical continuum concepts. In other approaches [18],[19] there are arguments advocating the implicit introduction of an Access CO located near the end-user to exploit fast and dynamic bandwidth allocation mechanisms, hence minimizing the use of connectivity modes reliant on resource overprovisioning. Finally, an additional argument in favor of such nodes in proximity to the end-user is that these nodes are filtering out a considerable amount of application-specific data junk coming from IoT terminal data. This data filtering is beneficial for reducing the traffic load sent towards the network backbone.

The main conclusion of this section is that an Access CO that is placed within a maximum distance of 10 km, ideally at a

distance of 5 km or less, becomes an indispensable asset to the emerging 6G access networks.

It is worth mentioning that the widespread introduction of Access COs in 6G infrastructures is going to bring additional, less apparent yet substantial consequences. In the realm of PtMP connectivity, when the physical distance between an OLT located at an Access CO and an ONU terminal is short, we can envisage PON implementations where performance is traded for lower cost. Indeed, a short physical distance limits the impact of detrimental physical effects, something that, in turn, allows us to use simpler optical layouts, fewer and/or less complex DSP blocks, and lower-performance and, hence, lower-cost optical components. All these parameters strongly affect both CapEx and OpEx and it is expected that such Short-Range PONs would positively contribute to the quest for lower cost solutions.

In the next section we present how this Access CO is integrated to the emerging 6G architecture.

B. Architectural Aspects of the Converged 6G Access Network.

A schematic illustration of a converged access network architecture is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1. Architectural overview of the North-South connectivity.

We postulate two groups of end-user terminals: (A) stationary or low mobility users; and (B) high mobility users. Group (A) users are served by means of a wireline connection,

exploiting either PtMP or PtP connectivity. For group (A) users, indoor connectivity may be achieved via WiFi x {x=7, 8}, LiFi and/or other similar short-range wireless technology. The two groups are shown separately at the bottom of Fig.1.

The traffic from group (A) users either terminates at the Far-Edge node, or it is optically bypassing this node, by means of optical multi-band technologies (OMB), to terminate at the Metro node (Edge) or even deeper in the network (in an optically transparent or non-transparent way). Based on the arguments presented in Section 2A, the Far-Edge node is located at a distance of 3-5 km from the end-user terminals, in the case of dense urban deployments, while it is found at 6-10 km in the case of rural deployments.

Connectivity for group (B) users is enabled using 5G/6G wireless cellular technologies; this also includes the case of fixed-wireless technologies. The wireless connectivity is terminated at a 6G cell, them being either macro or small; this work concentrates primarily on small cells. The aggregated traffic is transported from the 6G cell to the Far-Edge node by means of PtMP or PtP fiber optic connections. Alternatives that employ sub-THz wireless technology in conjunction with optical fiber connections are also considered in the context of fronthaul (FH) [20]; however, this case is not depicted in Fig.1 and not further considered here. The traffic flows from the two groups directed towards the terminal nodes (Access CO or Metro CO) depicted in Fig.1 constitute the *South-North* (S-N) traffic.

The Far-Edge node consists of pluggable PtMP OLTs or PtP transceiver terminal interfaces (i/f), L2 switches (typically arranged in a Spine-and-Leaf configuration in a folded-Clos architecture) and servers, deployed as micro-Datacenters (μ DCs) by means of which disaggregated virtualized functions and services are supported like, VNFs, AI/ML, Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC), and vDU/vCU and UPF/BNG implementations, as detailed in [21]. Moreover, μ DC may host the latency-sensitive components in a recursive execution of programs and/or the IoT data filtering, which aims to limit the loading of traffic towards the network backbone. Compared to regular-sized and scope DataCenters, the facilities Far-Edge nodes host are limited; however, these nodes do play a critical role in the implementation of the remote control of smart factories [19], [6] or precision-agriculture applications.

In the upstream direction, the aggregated traffic from the Access CO is transported to the Edge Node (Metro CO), where it is either terminated there or it is optically bypassing the node towards the location of a relevant Regional DataCenter (R-DC), as it is shown in Fig. 1 and in more detail in Fig.1 of [19]. An R-DC hosts far more IT and connectivity resources compared to a Far-Edge node so it may execute all processing intensive, hence, latency-relaxed, tasks a Far-Edge node may not and should not undertake.

In the aforementioned analysis, one may observe a number of optical bypassing points being set between: a) the end-user terminals and the Access CO (one-node bypassing); b) between the Access CO and the Metro CO (one-node bypassing); c) the end-user terminals and a different Metro CO or a Metro-Core node (two or multi-node bypassing). These bypass operations

materialize the conditions of an *optical continuum* where selected terminals or services may flexibly terminate at the μ DC, the R-DC or at a Warehouse DC. We observe that, as “intelligence” is spreading towards network periphery, the proposed connectivity architecture enables the QoS-performance constrained interconnection between end-user terminals and IT structures (μ DCs, R-DCs, and Warehouse DCs), as well as among different IT granularities, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

An important condition for a Far-Edge node to become ubiquitous is to support multi-tenancy. This means that the node should provide connectivity and security/privacy for cloud services in competing enterprises. Regarding the first requirement, the architectural framework for a Far-Edge node to support multi-tenancy in the S-N direction using passive multiplexing and transmission rather than switching (optical or electronic) is delineated in [16],[17]. Regarding the second requirement, quantum technology-based security solutions have now reached a level of maturity to deliver physical law-guaranteed end-to-end security that renders this technology a viable option to be incorporated in 6G networks.

Fig.2. The connectivity pattern between storage and processing terminals, them being end-users and IT nests.

Specifically, Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) solutions tailored for Access/Aggregation networks, either as stand-alone deployments or in association with Physically Unclonable Functions (PUFs), are considered to provide physically unbreakable end-to-end key transportation and/or device authentication to wireless routers and terminals [22],[23].

As part of the quest for a ubiquitous Far-Edge node, quantum technologies are integrated with classical data transportation networks using an SDN-enabled control plane. This is shown in Fig.1 where quantum network security is made possible via QKD PtP links, while the corresponding Key Management Systems (KMS) are deployed at the μ DC and the R-DC. The KMS is a key software module tasked to control and manage these systems in the context of SDN. The QKD link between a Macro-cell and the Access CO is implemented based on an optical fiber. On the other hand, the link between the Access CO and a small-cell could be based a free-space optics (FSO) technology (showed with a red broken line in Fig.1) while when a classical wireless technology needs to be used, the enhanced security is provided by means of a PUF-based authentication [22],[23].

C. West-East is a New Traffic Component in Access

The stringent latency performance resulting from the RU/DU split in C-RAN installations, along with analogous performance needs stemming from serverless computing and MEC concepts, have significant architectural implications.

Fig. 3. (a) A schematical illustration of the West-East connectivity obviating the South-North path; (b) W-E connectivity exploiting a constant-bit-rate technology by means of wavelength and subcarrier frequency; (c) E-W connectivity exploiting burst-mode technology and wavelength, frequency and time slicing (TFDM).

Due to the limited storage and processing resources of a μ DC, alternative connectivity solutions are necessary when these resources are temporarily overwhelmed or when the Far-Edge node gets overloaded with tasks [7]. As an example, if the Far-Edge Node runs multiple tasks, queuing delays may end up with loops of >1 ms in duration, stalling the corresponding ULLRC services. In this case, the services need to migrate to another IT facility. However, the typical South-North connectivity in the upstream (US) may not observe ULLRC

latency constraints as the corresponding distances are approaching or exceeding, sometimes by far, the 40 km round-trip accumulating $> 200 \mu$ s latency. The relative propagation delays as a function of distance are depicted in Fig.2 and based on the arguments presented in Section 2A, alternative architectural solutions are needed.

The need to migrate and transfer services and their operations to a different μ DC and Far-Edge node generates a novel West-East (W-E or E-W) traffic component inside the Access segment, as depicted in Fig. 3a. In the case where there is a high-load at the μ DC leading to long delays and the vDU service is not available anymore, or new services need to be introduced in the context of serverless computing, processes are migrated to an adjacent μ DC. Traffic still terminates at the original Access CO, but instead of being forwarded to the co-located μ DC, the traffic is aggregated and forwarded to the adjacent Access CO either in the W-E direction or the E-W direction.

A good candidate technology for the dynamic transportation of this traffic that balances throughput, latency and resource utilization is a sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver (SBVT) that exploits three-dimensional slicing [24],[25] to build a 400G system. After this scheme, wavelength and subcarrier frequency are time-shared between a number of terminals by means of the transportation architecture elaborated in [19].

It is pointed out that in [19], commercially available technologies, like TDM PONs, are used to interconnect emulated Metro nodes in the W-E direction, aiming to demonstrate the proof of concept (PoC) of dynamic packet/slot transportation and the integration, at control-plane level, of heterogeneous technologies. Although this scope is achieved, this PoC is facing considerable limitations: i) the aggregate capacity is 10 Gb/s which lags behind the current transportation trends; ii) the corresponding frame structure and the dynamic bandwidth allocation (DBA) are those of the commercial GPON and XGS-PON systems, which are based on the legacy 125 μ s frame duration. This is incompatible in the context of the current challenges even if the advances suggested in [13], [26] are applied.

To fully utilize the potential of the 400G TFDM technology in the context of this West-East connectivity, a paradigm shift is necessary, exploiting dynamic MAC-based reservation mechanisms to allow the lossless transportation of optical slots as low as 1 μ s in duration [27]-[29]. Towards this end, Fig.3 depicts the principle of operation of an FDMA slicing (3b) and of an FTDMA slicing (3c). In Fig. 3c, the numbers in the slots pertain to a slotted operation based on the methodology of [27]-[29] and they designate the hypothetical slots each Access CO adds along a West-East optically transparent path. Figure 3a illustrates the necessity for a shared sliceable transceiver technology, while Figures 3b and 3c emphasize the necessity for a suitable DBA/MAC technology that synchronizes the frequency and time slicing for these transceivers. The optical add-drop nodes (OADNs) could be as simple as 3-dB couplers as in [19] but also other advanced fast optical technologies may apply.

D. Overview of the Challenges in the Converged 6G Access

Following the outline of the architecture for the Access-Aggregation segments presented in the preceding sections, this section delineates the primary challenges confronting a converged 6G network.

- *Latency and Availability.* As I4.0 applications become key enablers of economic activity, resource availability should be ensured via mechanisms that does not degrade the corresponding latency performance. Having as an option to dynamically select the termination point of flows/services either at the Far-Edge node (Access CO) or at the Edge node (Metro CO) is an asset that can be used to ensure that the overall end-to-end latency performance is within the application's bounds, without compromising service availability.
- *Selecting the Optimal Transportation Granularity.* During the voice-era, the transportation granularity in access (PONs or PtP) was at least an order of magnitude higher than the given end-user's rate. There are several challenges that make it hard to maintain the same approach, such as a) technology constraints as these detailed in section 3; b) significant variability in end-user rates in the converged networks; c) the unpredictability of service penetration which is directly associated to geopolitical developments and the progress being made in other technology sectors (e.g. robotics); and d) a slowing down in the annual average growth of traffic accompanied coupled with sudden traffic surges. Consequently, it remains unresolved to determine the best aggregate capacity for PONs in the context of converged network. Simultaneously, the PtP connections are leveraging the DataCenter ecosystem. However, given the sheer volume of connections in the Access segment on a national scale, the incurred costs of a connectivity mode, like the PtP, that exclusively rely on underutilized and overprovisioning resources may be substantial.
- *The need to Wisely Exploit the Fiber Infrastructure.* It appears that several design decisions wireless technologies have made are based on the presumption of limitless fiber availability. Operators worldwide have, indeed, made an enormous investment in optical fiber; nonetheless, the utilization of this resource must be conducted judiciously, without stretching the fiber capability especially at the very last-drop segment.
- *Cell Densification in 6G.* In the 6G era, the small cells and new radio spectral bands are operated at frequencies which have inherently shorter range [30]. This is an objective process and, as a result, a considerably higher number of small cells are needed to maintain sufficient coverage. The impact of this densification on the aggregated transportation capacity towards the backbone and/or on fiber availability in the last-mile is only partially studied and understood today.

Sections 1 and 2 clearly indicate the imperative to introduce

Far-Edge nodes into the converged Access network architecture, marking a departure from a decades-old mind-set for the role of active nodes close to the end-user. The next section reviews the present state-of-the-art in connectivity, aiming to select the appropriate transportation capacity examples of wireless and wireline technologies for our modeling work. Moreover, we present the assumptions we have made in our dimensioning studies, highlighting the restrictions arising in real fiber last-mile deployments.

3. 6G TECHNOLOGIES AND OUR MODELING METHODOLOGY

In this work, we are poised to provide our point of view on the challenges outlines in section 2.D. Given that operators choose parameters such as spectrum, MIMO layers, passive splits, etc. according to specific national characteristics, which also may vary by geographic region, we opt to use only widely recognized parameters to assess the scalability of fiber deployments in the final segment of the Access network to accommodate various front-haul (FH) alternatives.

A. Objectives and Approach

In [7], dark fiber is acknowledged as a scarce resource that would not be utilized efficiently if only employed for PtP backhaul links in small-cell networks, while [8] points out that the largest cost benefit may arise from fiber infrastructure sharing, i.e., by avoiding a fiber infrastructure build specifically for mobile transport only.

The work of [8] summarizes the possible implementations through which wireline and wireless transportation systems concurrently share an optical fibre infrastructure as follows: a) they may share a PON mixing up residential and mobile traffic; b) they can create an overlay of connections by means of a separate wavelength over a PON layout; or c) each cell to employ a dark fiber to create a dedicated PtP connection.

A significant amount of effort has been undertaken to tackle the issues of mobile FH transportation outlined in 2.D by utilizing one of these architectural solutions. Several of these studies also include the benchmarking of the Capex/OpEx evaluation for the technology assessed in each instance. Indicatively, in [31] a TWDM PON configuration is considered to transport delay-sensitive services with strict latency performance requirements, while a cost analysis (CapEx/OpEx) is also presented as a function of latency constraints and passive splitting ratios. In [32], the total cost of ownership is used to assess the relative cost efficiency of Ethernet-based mobile fronthaul using PtP WDM links. The work of [33] goes one step further, and by using an average cell density, it estimates the transportation cost in sub-6GHz small cell deployments using PtMP layouts for XGS PONs and 25G TDM PONs.

Our study considers the FH option for the alternatives (a)-(c) above, and it capitalizes and further expands upon the methodology presented in [33]. In particular, we examine the fiber utilization rate in the segment between an Access CO and end-user terminals, and we deduce the number of the corresponding transportation interfaces as a function of the line rates for group (A) and group (B) users. For the latter group, we exclusively assume small-cells using mmWave band

technologies across several functional splits supporting RF bandwidths of 100 MHz, 200 MHz, and 400 MHz.

B. Wireline and Wireless Transportation Line Rates

We consider wireline technologies first which are further subdivided into PtMP and PtP. Regarding PtMP transportation interfaces based on TDMA techniques, 25G and 50G TDM PONs are on the road to commercialization and research is shifted to identify the next milestones [34]. The authors of [35] conclude that a 100G PON based on IM-DD technology is feasible, while it is speculated that beyond that limit, the wavelength dimension needs to step in, creating $N \times 50G$ or $N \times 100G$ aggregate rates. Indeed, [36] uses 100G technology as a base-line to demonstrate a 400G system based on two wavelengths and dual polarization. The authors of [37] report a single-carrier 200G coherent TDM PON based on an experiment conducted over a field-deployed fiber. Finally, as already detailed, two-dimensional sliced TFDMA PON is regarded as a viable alternative to pure TDM PON technologies [24], [25].

TABLE I
SMALL CELL TRANSPORTATION LINE RATES

Option 2 (F1)			
	RF Bandwidth		
MIMO Layers	100 MHz	200 MHz	400 MHz
2	808 Mb/s	1.62 Gb/s	3.23 Gb/s
4	1.62 Gb/s	3.23 Gb/s	6.46 Gb/s
Option 7.3			
MIMO Layers	100 MHz	200 MHz	400 MHz
2	1.033 Gb/s	2.067 Gb/s	4.11 Gb/s
4	2.067 Gb/s	4.11 Gb/s	8.22 Gb/s
Option 7.2			
MIMO Layers	100 MHz	200 MHz	400 MHz
2	6.57 Gb/s	13.15 Gb/s	26.31 Gb/s
4	13.15 Gb/s	26.3 Gb/s	52.61 Gb/s
Option 7.1			
MIMO Layers	100 MHz	200 MHz	400 MHz
2	13.42 Gb/s	26.31 Gb/s	52.62 Gb/s
4	26.84 Gb/s	52.63 Gb/s	105.2 Gb/s
Option 8 (CPRI)			
MIMO Layers	100 MHz	200 MHz	400 MHz
2	19.58 Gb/s	39.16 Gb/s	78.33 Gb/s
4	39.16 Gb/s	78.363 Gb/s	156.67 Gb/s

On the other hand, the PtP connections are leveraging the Ethernet intra-datacenter ecosystem featuring line-rates of 25 Gb/s, 100 Gb/s and 200 Gb/s.

Next, we take into account the transportation rates associated

with 5G/6G wireless technologies. In particular, we list in Table I the transportation rates associated with small cells for Options 2, 7.1, 7.2, 7.3 and 8. These line-rates reported in Table I are in-line with the approach of [21], assuming no data compression. The formalism used for the computation of the rates in Table I is detailed in [38],[39] and the figures are in very good agreement with the rates reported in [26] in accordance with the assumptions outlined below. The dark shading of cells is explained in section D.

i) The FEC and, more broadly, the transportation overhead are typically vendor-specific technical attributes, and their actual implementation affects latency figures. Consequently, this study only considers widely accepted assumptions on this overhead.

ii) While the wireless uplink (UL) and downlink (DL) rates are likely to differ, and despite there being a provision for asymmetric transportation rates in TDM PON technologies [40], this difference has no impact on the dimensioning of a converged access network where groups (A) and (B) utilize the same PtMP infrastructure. Therefore, only the maximum of the UL/DL rates is listed in Table I.

iii) Compression is widely explored in 5G/6G wireless transportation technologies, and many of the services mentioned in section 2.A. are also sensitive to delays, we avoid considering configurations that rely on compression, as its impact on latency is difficult to predict.

iv) For similar reasons, we avoid making any assumptions about any modulation compression techniques. Indeed, we can achieve a lower transportation rate by reducing the modulation cardinality, an approach which also improves the robustness of the channel but, in effect, limits the number of active users.

v) We have taken into account the discrepancy between the context Option 6 is used in [21] and the corresponding definition for the Split-6 of 3GPP [41],[42]. This discrepancy has its origin to diverging optimization transportation strategies: ITU-T's Option 6 assumes aggressive compression of time-domain samples (e.g., quantization, pruning), reducing transport rates. On the other hand, 3GPP's Split-6 transports frequency-domain resource elements (REs) post-FFT without compression, leading to higher rates.

Consequently, ITU-T's Option 6 exhibits lower transport rates than Option 7.2, while 3GPP's Split-6 (uncompressed) exceeds the rates of Split-7.2. As our focus is on uncompressed/low-latency scenarios (Section 2.A), Option 6 is excluded from further analysis. As a final remark, Small-Cell Forum's (SCF) adoption of 3GPP splits (e.g., Split-7.2) over ITU-T's Option 6 [21] reflects the industry's preference for uncompressed, latency-robust fronthaul which further validates to consider only the transportation rates as of Table I.

C. Fiber Deployments in the Last-Mile

The proliferation of 6G networks is unthinkable without a dense fiber infrastructure. Fig.1 depicts the generic architecture for the access segment, demonstrating that the Access CO becomes a point of convergence for all active fibers in the last-drop. Obviously, not all of these fibers terminate at the Access CO and there is a direct PtMP and PtP connectivity to the Metro

CO node.

Fig. 4 illustrates the connectivity pattern between the Access CO and the end-user terminal in further detail. In particular, the Access CO is the termination/origin point for several fiber cables towards the end-user. Typically, in large metropolitan cities there are several cables arranged in ducts (typically, there can be up to 48 cables per duct) and each of these cables has 24-144 fibers with 96 being a common number.

Fig. 4. Nodes and connectivity for the wireline Access last-drop

Several European network operators deploy *Remote Cabinets* (RCs) between an Access CO and the end-user terminal, such as a single fiber cable interconnects multiple RCs.

Typically, up to 24 fibers are terminated per RC, allowing for the interconnection of up to 4 x RCs with a 96-fiber cable, and up to 6 x RCs with a 144-fiber cable. Undoubtedly, these figures fluctuate among operators or even within a specific operator's network; nonetheless, the practical reality is that there exists a maximum number of fibers assigned to each RC, and this number is often set by the physical dimensions of the RC.

To increase the number of end-user terminals served within a designated neighborhood (aka, to enhance connectivity), a new RC can be placed adjacent to the existing installation, therefore doubling the capacity. The alternative is a specific RC to be replaced with a new unit that is able to support the termination of up to 48 fibers per RC, but operators want to extend the lifespan of their assets, as replacing cabinets is a costly and capital-intensive endeavor.

Fig. 4 allows us to visualize the connectivity arrangement. In particular, it is observed that four fibers are allocated to the second RC in the chain. Of these, two fibers are utilized for PtMP deployments, while the remaining two fibers are designated for PtP connections.

Fig. 5 further delineates this two-stage fiber deployment in greater detail, comprising a primary and a secondary subnetwork. The primary subnetwork consists exclusively of PtP connections between the Access CO and the RC. To create a 1:64 PtMP tree, the relevant fibers in the primary subnet first

undergo an initial split of 1:4 at the RC, followed by a further division of 1:16 (conversely, two stages of 1:8 split are used). In an alternative deployment scheme, the second dividing stage transpires at the end-user premises after the demarcation point. Concerning the secondary subnetwork, there exists a maximum number of fiber connections that a single RC can accommodate. This number ranges between 384 and 576 fiber segments, through which both PtMP and PtP connections are implemented.

Having defined the necessary parameters, we are ready to conclude the practical limits of these deployments. Maximum connectivity is realized when two collocated RCs are implemented, and under the default configuration, there can be between 6 and 12 fibers in the primary network destined to implement PtMP trees within the secondary subnet while the remaining fibers are meant to implement PtP connections. With modifications and re-deployments of splitters and other auxiliary optical components within each of these RCs, there is potential for up to 16 PtMP trees at the expense of PtP connections. In this case, the RC supports up to 8 PtP connections for Enterprises, Marco cells, and QKD key transit, resulting in a total of 24 fibers per RC.

Fig. 5. End-to-End connectivity in the last-drop

In this work, we use two parameters as figures-of-merit to evaluate the scalability of various 6G deployments: the first is the number of fibers utilized by each deployment at the RC in the primary subnet (prior to the passive splitting stages). This parameter is estimated by eq. (1) below:

$$Utilization = \frac{\text{Fibers used in primary subnet}}{\text{Total fibers available per RC (e.g. 24)}} \quad (1)$$

A significant concept employed in this work is the categorization of limits pertaining to fiber utilization thresholds. Typically, European operators, including TelecomItalia and BT, categorize three usage regimes for fiber utilization: less than 30% (green), between 30% and 70% (yellow), and greater than 70% (red). As the average number of fibers in the primary subnet for an RC is 24, a fiber usage of ≤ 7 is considered as 'low', in the range between 8 and 15 as 'moderate' and ≥ 16 as 'high'.

The second figure of merit we use in this work is the number

of the corresponding interfaces at the Access CO that support PtMP and PtP terminations. In Section D below, we present the methodology we have adopted to estimate the values of these parameters.

D. Modeling Assumptions and Methodology

The resource utilization figures are derived with the aid of the grid illustrated in Fig. 6. It comprises equidistant RCs symmetrically positioned around an Access CO located at the center of the grid. The Manhattan Street topology enables the derivation of results that are independent of the specifics of real-world deployment topologies, which would otherwise hinder the generalization of these results from this study. To carry out the dimensioning study, we have used the data an operator has provided which encompasses the population and the number of households per RC and per Access CO in a moderately dense urban environment of a big city (around 1 million inhabitants) as summarized in Table II. It is pointed out that dense urban or suburban environments, as well as cities of different size, would be based on a different grid size and parameters.

Fig.6. Schematic layout of the grid that is used for the dimensioning of the Access last-drop.

Two deployment scenarios are considered in this work. In the first, the user groups (A) and (B) utilize PtMP and PtP transportation infrastructures, respectively, which are completely decoupled. In the second scenario, we assume the opposite: i.e., a single PtMP network is shared between the two groups, and the deployment is used to transport the traffic from both user groups (A) and (B); this arrangement is the typical deployment scheme for TDM PON implementations.

The number of small cells in Table II is deduced by assuming that they are deployed across the sides of a streets within the $200\text{m} \times 200\text{m}$ area each RC covers; the exact allocation depends on the coverage distance of the particular small cell family. Details on how small cells are distributed are given in

[33].

Considering the upstream of the South-North direction, we assume that 50% of the traffic terminates at the Access CO while the remaining traffic terminates at the Metro CO. The actual termination point does not influence the fiber utilization rate at the primary subnet; however, it does affect the number of active interfaces (OLTs or pluggable transceivers) required at the Access CO.

Regarding wireline transportation technology, we assumed that the PtMP passive networks are served by means of 25G and 50G TDM-PONs. This means that neither of these technologies is qualified to transport the dark-shaded cells in Table I.

TABLE II
REALISTIC URBAN DEPLOYMENT SCENARIOS

	# Elements	Geographic coverage
Access CO	1	2.5 km ² (1.6 km x 1.6 km)
Cabinets (RCs)	64	0.04 km ² (200m x 200m)
Macro Cells	8	0.31 km ² (560m x 560m)
Small Cells	64 – 1,024	2.5 km ² (1.6 km x 1.6 km)
Households per Cabinet	209	0.04 km ² (200m x 200m)

In this case, still in the context of passive PtMP topologies, a 200G digital subcarrier multiplexed (DSCM) PtMP system [43] is considered instead, using 8 x 25G sub-carrier frequencies in the upstream direction and 8 x 25G in the downstream direction. One possible implementation of the 25G line-rate is made by using a source with a baud-rate of 3.5Gbaud with PDM-16QAM modulation format, which sufficient to transport the 25G nominal rate plus FEC overhead.

For PtP links, we consider constant bit-rate (CBR) transceivers of the class 25G LR and 100G LR at the Fx interface and the class 10G LR at the F1 interface.

The passive splitting ratios are typically 1:64 and 1:32; a passive split of 1:16 is also considered, but in general it is not preferred.

A. Traffic parameters

For the users in the group (A), we have assumed that their nominal line rates range between 500 Mb/s and 3 Gb/s featuring a sustained rate of 0.3 (i.e., 30% of the peak nominal rate). We note that certain European operators already offer such nominal (peak) rates and, in some cases, even higher (e.g., 10 Gb/s).

The group (B) users are exclusively small-cells deployed with a typical inter-cell distance between 200 m and 50 m [44] and with rates as in Table I for RF bandwidths of 100 MHz and 400 MHz.

It is pointed out that no fiber protection/restoration needs are considered in this work something that would set further limits to the available fiber at the RC.

4. RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN THE LAST-DROP.

Having specified the topology, the traffic parameters, and the technologies, we proceed to dimension the resource utilization rates under the two deployment schemes.

A. Dimensioning the Scheme with Parallel Infrastructures

We assume two decoupled infrastructures, a PtMP for group (A) and a PtP for group (B), that operate in parallel but completely decoupled. Depending on the selected peak-rate for end users in group (A), the PON split is selected to match the maximum capacity of the TDM PON family to this line-rate for the number of users in Table II. For example, to serve the group (A) end-users by means of a 25G TDM PON, a line rate of 1 Gb/s with a sustain rate 0.3, a 1:64 split suffice, but when the rate is 2 Gb/s, the split drops to 1:32 while for 3 Gb/s/user a 1:16 split is necessary.

The results of the dimensioning studies are shown in Fig.7. Fig.7a shows the PtMP dimensioning and in particular, the passive split of the PON, the number of PtMP (PON) trees per RC, and the number of line-terminations (LTs) per Access CO (assuming that 50% of the traffic terminates at this node).

Peak Rate	25G PON			50G PON		
	Split	PtMP/Cabinet	LTs/CO	Split	PtMP/Cabinet	LTs/CO
500 Mb/s	1:64	4	128	1:64	4	128
1 Gb/s	1:64	4	128	1:64	4	128
2 Gb/s	1:32	7	224	1:64	4	128
3 Gb/s	1:16	14	448	1:32	7	224

(a)

	Small Cells 200 m	Small Cells 100 m	Small Cells 50 m
Total # Cells	256	512	1024
Cells/RC	4	8	16
PtP Fibers/RC (Grey)	4	8	16
PtP Fibers/RC (CWDM)	-	1	1

(b)

Fig.7. Fiber consumption per RC for decoupled infrastructures. In (a) for group (A) while in (b) for group (B).

Fig. 7b enumerates the total number of small cells per Access CO and the number of small cells inside the vicinity of a single RC to which it offers connectivity. The third and the fourth lines illustrate the number of fibers utilized in the primary subnet, which is contingent upon the PtP technology. In particular, the third line shows the fiber utilization in the primary and the secondary subnet when grey transceivers are employed. One may observe that this option leads to a high value for fiber utilization, which becomes unsustainable when the inter-cell distance goes down to the lower limit of 50 meters. The fourth line is showcasing the fiber utilization in the primary subnet when colored transceivers are used instead, adopting a CWDM scheme (e.g., 1271 nm–1611 nm, spaced 20nm apart; see Fig. 1) assuming a WDM mux/demux is placed at the RC. In this CWDM example, fiber utilization in the primary subnet is well

within acceptable limits as long as group (A) end-user rates are up to 2 Gb/s; the number of fibers used in the secondary subnet remains the same as in the case with grey interfaces.

For the deployments as of Fig. 6a, when group (A) end-users reach a rate of 2 Gb/s, fiber utilization with a 25G TDM PON becomes excessive but manageable, necessitating an additional RC alongside the current one. This is a breaking point that highlights the attractiveness of a 50G TDM PON, as it stalls the fiber usage for PtMP trees in the primary subnet. When group (A) end-users achieve a rate of 3 Gb/s, only a 50G TDM PON is feasible.

Nevertheless, since both the PtMP trees and PtP links draw from the same fiber pool in the primary subnet, the total fiber utilization is estimated by adding up the corresponding individual utilization figures. To facilitate the visualization of fiber utilization rates, the relevant cells in Fig. 7 are color-coded. According to the reasoning outlined in section 3.C regarding the widely accepted utilization figures, the colors green, yellow and red are used to denote low, moderate and high utilization values, respectively. Likewise, to account for the overall utilization, the color of the arrows signifies fiber consumption due to the simultaneous use of both PtMP and PtP fibers. For instance, allocating 3 Gb/s per residential user with a 25G TDM PON system renders an intra-cell distance of 50 m unfeasible when utilizing grey interfaces, as it necessitates 30 fibers in the primary subnet, so the color of the broken arrow that designates this particular combination is red. Conversely, when a 50G TDM PON is used with a 3 Gb/s user rate for the residential users and a 100-meter inter-cell distance, it necessitates 15 fibers in the primary network to accommodate the traffic of group (A) and group (B) users. Therefore, this combination is designated with a yellow dashed arrow.

It is pointed out that when the small-cell connectivity is made using PtP connections, fiber consumption depends only on the number of small cells within the area of a single RC and it is independent of the functional split and the small cell's RF bandwidth. However, the selection of the nominal line-rate of the grey or the colored interface does depend on the function split, and the corresponding transceivers should match Table I line-rates.

A final remark is that the number of fibers in the secondary subnet is sufficient to support the connectivity requirements arising from Table II, as the total number of end users from group (A) and group (B) combined is never more than 225.

B. Dimensioning the Shared Passive Infrastructure Scheme

In this scenario, residential users and small-cells utilize the same PtMP tree. The number of small cells and residential users to be serviced by PON is constrained by the rate of the latter, the inter-cell distance of the former, and the transportation capacity of the TDM PON family.

Table III displays the resource utilization based on the rates listed in Table I and the parameters given in Section 3D.A. In particular, we contemplate the functional splits 7.3 and 7.2 for small cells with 2x2 and 4x4 MIMO layers, designated as $M=2$ and $M=4$, respectively, and a 50-meter distance between micro-cells. Based on the figures of Table I, neither 25G nor 50G

TDM PONs meet the requirements for being used to transport data from small cells under the split 7.1. Therefore, we limit our analysis for the splits 7.2, 7.2 and the Option 2 (F1 rate).

The values in the respective matrix cells of Table III read as follows: i) the first line in the cell of each column designates the passive split (e.g. 1:64); ii) the second line in each cell shows the number of fibers in the primary subnet utilized per RC (out of the maximum number of fibers per RC e.g. 24) which is determined by the specific combination of small cells rates per split and the residential user-rate density as outlined in Table II; iii) the third line enumerates the number of LTs at the Access CO per RC required to transport the corresponding capacity.

TABLE III

RESOURCE UTILIZATION OF PtMP TOPOLOGY WITH 50M INTER-CELL DISTANCE

Peak Rate	Option 2 M=2 @ 3.2 Gb/s M=4 @ 6.4 Gb/s	Option 7.3 M=2 @ 4.1 Gb/s M=4 @ 8.2 Gb/s	Option 7.2 M=2 @ 26.3Gb/s M=4 @ 52.6Gb/s	
500 Mb/s M = 2	1:64 4/24 4 x 50G	1:64 4/24 4 x 50G	1:32 16 x 50G grey 16/24	1:64 16 x 50G TWDM 4/24
500 Mb/s M = 4	1:64 4/24 4 x 50G	1:64 4/24 4 x 50G	1:64 8/24 8 x DSCM & 4x50G	
1 Gb/s M = 2	1:64 4/24 4 x 50G	1:64 4/24 4 x 50G	1:32 16 x 50G grey 16/24	1:64 16 x 50G TWDM 4/24
1 Gb/s M = 4	1:64 4/24 4 x 50G	1:64 5/24 5 x 50G	1:64 8/24 8 x DSCM + 4x50G	
2 Gb/s M = 2	1:64 5/24 5 x 50G	1:64 4/24 4 x 50G	1:32 16 x 50G grey 16/24	1:64 16 x 50G TWDM 4/24
2 Gb/s M = 4	1:64 6/24 6 x 50G	1:32 8/24 8 x 50G	1:64 8/24 8 x DSCM + 4x50G	
3 Gb/s M = 2	1:32 7/24 7 x 50G	1:32 8/24 8 x 50G	1:32 16 x 50G grey 16/24	1:64 16 x 50G TWDM 4/24
3 Gb/s M = 4	1:32 7/24 7 x 50G	1:32 8/24 8 x 50G	1:32 8/24 8 x DSCM + 7x50G	

The cells in the case of split 7.2 featuring 2x2 MIMO (M=2) are further divided into two: the left cell delineates the parameters under the assumption of a single-channel 50G TDM PON OLT, whereas the right cell illustrates the scenario a TWDM 50G PON is employed [40],[45]. For instance, when the peak rate of group (A) users is 2 Gb/s and there are 16 small cells, then 16 x 50G TDM-PON LTs are necessary at the Access CO and/or Metro CO to terminate the traffic arising from this RC. When a single-channel 50G PON's OLT is used, 16 out of the 24 fibers are utilized in the primary subnet per RC. On the other hand, with a 50G/ch. TWDM PON and 4 channels (separate wavelengths), 4 out of the 24 fibers are employed in the primary subnet.

The introduction of the TWDM PON is intended to mirror the introduction of colored transceivers in the case of PtP connections in section 4.A. It is pointed out that the number of

OLTs at the Access/Metro COs in the present case remains the same regardless of the type of OLT used (single or multi-wavelength). Nonetheless, the results clarify the advantages of utilizing a unified PtMP architecture, since the aggregate capacity, facilitated by WDM, is multiplied by the number of OLTs operating at different nominal wavelengths. This process saves a lot of fiber and it presents a clear alternative in the case of fiber exhaustion.

Extending the methodology outlined in sections 3.C and 4.A, fiber utilization is illustrated through color-coded cells in Table III: the colors green, yellow and red are used to denote low, moderate and high utilization values, respectively. It is observed that fiber utilization under split 7.2 with a (single channel) 50G TDM PON OLT becomes critical.

Furthermore, small cells employing a 4x4 MIMO antenna under split 7.2 are possible only by means of a 200G DSCM system, which is a technology inherently compatible with PtMP deployments. The integration of DSCM, a C-band technology, with TDM-PONs results in optical multi-band transportation technology overlays on the same shared passive infrastructure. This overlay allows for the flexible use of 1:64 or 1:32 passive splits so the total number of PtMP trees and LTs is minimized.

TABLE IV

RESOURCES AT ACCESS CO (50M INTER-CELL DISTANCE)

Peak Rate	Parallel Infrastructures (PtMP & PtP)	Single PtMP Infrastructure
2 Gb/s M = 2	512 x 100G (LR4/PAM4 or CWDM) 128 x 50G LTs (TDM)	512 x 50G LTs (TDM or TWDM)
2 Gb/s M = 4	512 x 100G (LR4/PAM4 or CWDM) 128 x 50G LTs (TDM)	256 x 200G DSCM 128 x 50G (TDM or TWDM)
3 Gb/s M = 2	512 x 100G (LR4/PAM4 or CWDM) 224 x 50G LTs (TDM)	512 x 50G (TDM or TWDM)
3 Gb/s M = 4	512 x 100G (LR4/PAM4 or CWDM) 224 x 50G LTs (TDM)	256 x 200G DSCM 224 x 50G (TDM or TWDM)

Nonetheless, the introduction of DSCM PtMP technology comes with a price. As the line rate when 4x4 MIMO is used is 52.6 Gb/s, it requires the introduction of flow splitting/reassembly mechanism utilizing 3 x 25G subcarrier frequencies, which exacerbates latency and introduces synchronization concerns. Moreover, since up to 8 subcarrier frequencies are available in the upstream (or downstream), a maximum of two small cells can be allocated per PtMP, leading to 8 PON trees for each RC and a rather poor utilization of the subcarrier frequencies. In principle, one may take advantage of the asymmetry in the UL/DL line-rates to fine-tune the utilization of a DSCM system by allocating more subcarrier frequencies, e.g. in the DL direction. This task, is beyond the scope of this work and it will not be discussed any further.

Table IV uses the parameters of Table III for small cells under split 7.2 to benchmark the parallel and the single shared infrastructure schemes in terms of the total number of interfaces

at the Access CO. We consider only the cases where group (A) users are assigned 2 Gb/s and 3 Gb/s, and we also assume that 50% of the traffic terminates at this node.

We conclude that in the case with 2x2 MIMO antennas, the shared PtMP arrangement is clearly advantageous in terms of the total number of interfaces and in terms of cost, too, when comparing widely acceptable cost values for the 100G PtP transceivers (LR4 or PAM4) with those for 50G TDM PON OLTs. Conversely, in the context of small cells equipped with 4x4 MIMO antennas, the advantages of employing PtMP are more contentious, as PtP connectivity necessitates the utilization of twice as many interfaces, which, however, are well-established within the DataCentre ecosystem, unlike the relatively novel DSCM systems.

Finally, Table V illustrates the per RC resource utilization as a function of the inter-cell distance, which varies between 200 m and 50m [44]. The results are obtained for group (A) users with 2 Gb/s peak rate and small cells implementing split 7.2, with grey interfaces, $M = 2$, and an RF bandwidth of 400 MHz.

TABLE V
RESOURCE UTILIZATION DUE TO CELL DENSIFICATION

	Inter-Cell Distance 200 m	Inter-Cell Distance 100 m	Inter-Cell Distance 50 m
Cells/RC	4	8	16
Single PtMP	4 x 50G LTs 4/24 Fibers	8 x 50G LTs 8/24 Fibers	16 x 50G LTs 16/24 Fibers
Parallel Infrastructure	1 x 100G LP4 4 x 50G LTs 5/24 Fibers	8 x 100G LR4 4 x 50G LTs 8/24 Fibers	16 x 100G LR4 4x50G LTs 20/24 Fibers

The results indicate that even with longer inter-cell distances, like 100m, there is considerable utilization of resources, which, when it comes to fiber utilization, means that a second RC is needed next to the original one regardless of the selected transportation scheme.

5. BENCHMARKING SCALABILITY IN THE CONTEXT OF FUTURE PASSIVE OPTICAL NETWORKS

This section examines the potential effects of employing alternative solutions for very high capacity PONs [24],[25],[36],[37],[40],[43],[45] on resource consumption in the context of future converged networks. Based on the analysis made in the previous sections, we investigate to what extent these alternatives address the scalability concerns of 6G networks. Having as a target a 400G PtMP passive optical network, the following alternatives are considered:

- A hybrid scheme consisting of 50G TDM PONs and a symmetric DSCM PtMP with 16 x 50G subcarriers CBR (8 subcarriers for upstream and 8 subcarriers downstream)
- A TFDM PON consisting of 16 x 50G subcarrier frequencies with each frequency being TDMA shared i.e. it is operated in burst-mode (with 8 subcarriers serving the upstream and 8 subcarriers the downstream)
- A coherent, single-carrier, 400G TDM PON
- A coherent 400G TDM PON, consisting of 2 x single-

carrier 200G TDM PON

- A hybrid scheme consisting of 50G TDM PONs and PtP connections

It is pointed out that no attempt is made to address the many and important technological challenges associated with the materialization of these interfaces; neither are we trying to address the acute challenges of critical subsystems like the parallelization/serialization of traffic flows or the optimal frame size and the DBA that is necessary to support uRLLC services. All these questions are critical, but they are outside the scope of this work. However, we need to point out few generic but important technological differences between these alternatives. The 50G line rate/subcarrier for the TFDM PON is built by using a source with a baud rate of 7 Gbaud with PDM-16QAM modulation format. The total transportation bandwidth in this case is $7 \text{ Gbaud} \times 4 \text{ bits/symbol (16QAM)} \times 2 \text{ (PDM)} = 56 \text{ Gb/s}$ (50G nominal after FEC overhead). This arrangement contrasts with 50G TDM PON, which typically uses NRZ or PAM-4 at 25 GHz (for NRZ) or 12.5 GHz (for PAM-4), demanding higher-frequency electronics. The lower nominal rate the electronics operate at (7 GHz vs. 25 GHz) reduces power consumption and simplifies DSP complexity, aligning with carbon/economic goals the European Commission has set. Moreover, the subcarriers can be activated progressively (e.g., start with $4 \times 50\text{G}$ for 200G, and then scale to $16 \times 50\text{G}$ for 400G), matching 6G's phased rollout. Additionally, TFDM's compatibility with ITU-T G.9804.1 [45] allows reuse of existing components (e.g., optics, DSP blocks). Similar arguments may apply for the single-carrier coherent 400G TDM PON.

TABLE VI
DIMENSIONING FUTURE 6G CONVERGED TECHNOLOGIES

	Split 7.2 M=2 (26.3 Gb/s)	Split 7.2 M=4 (52.6 Gb/s)	Split 7.1 M=2 (52.6 Gb/s)	Split 7.1 M=4 (105.2 Gb/s)
Hybrid 50G TDM PON & PtP Links	128 x 50G LTs & 512 100G CWDM	128 x 50G LTs & 512 100G CWDM (16λ)	128 x 50G LTs & 512 100G CWDM (16λ)	128 x 50G LTs & 512 200G CWDM (16λ)
Hybrid DSCM 16 x 50GHz & 50G TDM PON	-	128 x 50G LTs & 256 x DSCM LTs	128 x 50G LTs & 256 x DSCM LTs	128 x 50G LTs & 512 x DSCM LTs
TFDM 400G PON (16 x 50G)	128 x 400G LTs	256 x 400G LTs	256 x 400G LTs	512 x 400G LTs
Coherent TDM PON 400G (single λ)	64 x 400G LTs	96x 400G LTs	96 x 400G LTs	128 x 400G LTs
Coherent TDM PON 400G (2x200G)	64 x 400G LTs	96 x 400G LTs	96 x 400G LTs	128 x 400G LTs

Here, we limit our analysis to the complexity associated with the number of interfaces each alternative provides when placed at the Access CO, despite the aforementioned qualitative difference between the corresponding technologies. For this purpose, we assume an end-user of group (A) with a 2 Gb/s peak rate, while group (B) employs the splits 7.2 and 7.1 and 400 MHz RF bandwidth. We set the inter-cell distance for the small cells to 50 m. The results of the benchmarking are listed in Table VI. To make the calculations transparent, we elaborate on the values listed in the second row and second column of Table VI; by using the numbers quoted in Table III, which

indicates 8 x DSCM and 4 x 50G TDM PONs per RC (sixth row, third column), and assuming that 50% of the traffic terminates at the Access CO, the total number of 50G TDM PONs is 128, while the total number of DSCM 50G subcarriers reaches 256.

To dimension the single-carrier 400G TDM PON we have assumed a 1:128 passive split. This extension is viable when considering fiber availability in the secondary subnet and the practical limitations within RCs to attain a 1:128 split. On the other hand, the 2 x 200G TDM PON still employs a 1:64 split.

The first conclusion of this analysis is that there is no need to utilize more than 8 PtMP trees per RC in any of the alternatives. In fact, only the solutions employing a DSCM with 50 GHz spaced subcarrier frequencies require 8 PtMP trees per RC. Undoubtedly, his granularity, let alone the DSCM with 25GHz spacing, is suboptimal for low-layer splits and antennas with more than 2x2 MIMO layers. However, the TFDM PON variant (that may employ a commercially available CBR DSCM system in the downstream adopting the legacy approach of TDM PONs having CBR flows in this direction) remains of great interest as it allows the flexible allocation of bandwidth/subcarrier frequencies to deployments featuring a spatial asymmetry, i.e., one PtMP tree requires more capacity than the adjacent one. In this case, the redundant subcarriers in one PtMP tree could be allocated to adjacent PtMP trees with the aid of additional optical elements. An analysis of this case is beyond the scope of the current work.

The two brands of 400G TDM PONs (single- λ or with 2- λ) utilize up to 4 fibers per RC in the primary subnet. The single-carrier coherent PON systems are the most efficient ones in terms of the total number of LTs at the Access CO, while the two hybrid schemes are those with the highest number of interfaces. Smaller number of terminal points also means fewer ports are required at the Ethernet switch in the Access CO to facilitate packet-optical deployments, as in [32].

A. Flexible Service Termination in the Upstream

There is an additional reason why the alternative consisting of 2 x single-carrier 200G TDM PON is considered here. In the upstream direction, traffic that originates from the given ONU, it may transport both uRLLC and mMTC services.

The former, characterized by stringent latency limits, terminates at the Access CO while the latency tolerant eMBB services may terminate at the Edge Node (Metro) or at service points even deeper in the network. We recall the analysis of section 2 that a Far-Edge node hosts limited IT resources which are scarce at this node so a dual termination scheme also serves the purpose to use consciously the compute and storage resources at this node.

Fig. 8. Flexibility in service termination offered by the TFDM PON and the 2 x 200G TDM PON alternatives.

This is schematically shown in Fig. 8 which shows that while one channel (green, dotted line) terminates at the Access CO, a second channel originating from the same ONU at a different wavelength (broken line, in purple) terminates at the Metro CO. This way, by means of the appropriate slicing, the same ONU ensures dual connectivity, i.e., termination at the Access CO and the Metro CO.

In this respect, among the alternatives we consider in this section, the single-carrier 400G TDM PON is the least flexible option as it can only have a single termination point. The TFDM PON 16 x 50 GHz and the 2 x 200G TDM PON alternatives are the most flexible options. This assessment complicates the final verdict on the optimal solution, as each option presents advantages and disadvantages.

6. CONCLUSIONS

6G networks are emerging as the central linking institution for I4.0 as they make possible the interconnection and integration of a wide range of heterogeneous technologies, services, and applications. The foundation of cloud-integrated 6G networks is the amalgamation of wireline and wireless technology, something that leads to significant architectural changes. Performance-related requirements in connectivity networks and the quest for better quality-of-experience for the end-users are reversing the model followed in the previous decades where processing and electronics were pushed deeper in the network. To better serve the diverse needs of end-users, intelligence is now spread to the network periphery closer to the end-user, and a Far-Edge node is emerging as an indispensable asset, reshaping the balance between passive multiplexing and transmission and data processing and storage.

Far-Edge nodes, aka Access COs, should be carefully architected to maintain a balance between performance and an affordable cost for the operators; otherwise, they will never become ubiquitous, hindering the advancement of the digital economy as a whole. To support the requested connectivity, operators have massively invested in the fiberization of the last-drop. Nevertheless, fiber remains a scarce commodity, and the plans of converged wireline and wireless technologies should account for this factor.

The architectural changes linked to 5G/6G C-RAN are raising the question of whether it is preferable to utilize parallel, entirely decoupled fiber infrastructures for two technologies or if a PtMP tree represents a better alternative. Although macro-cells are undeniably better supported by PtP connections, especially when antennas with massive MIMO are deployed,

the optimal connectivity mode when residential and small cells share the same infrastructure remains debated in the prospect of multi-Gb/s line rates for the former and mmWave technology exceeding 100 MHz RF bandwidth for the latter.

In this work, we consider resource consumption as a performance indicator through which we assess the efficacy of alternative transportation schemes of a converged network infrastructure. Specifically, based on realistic geospatial data supplied by operators, we estimate fiber availability in the last-mile as well as the number of interfaces at the Access CO. It turns out that the fiber utilization rate for both the parallel and shared passive infrastructure alternatives remains at feasible levels only when colored technology in the form of WDM is introduced.

Moreover, it appears that the 25G and 50G TDM PON products that are about to enter the market are coming relatively late, as the aggregate capacity they provide is not well-suited to address the small cell densification in the context of lower-layer functional splits. The conclusion is exactly the opposite, though, when a high-layer split is implemented by means of the F1 interface (Option 2) as Table III suggests. Finally, we have benchmarked alternative 400G PtMP technology solutions against the resources, and in particular the number of fibers and the interfaces needed required to accommodate the capacity in the last drop. The 400G aggregate capacity seems to be the optimal value to address the combined impact of high-line rates from end-users and lower-layer functional splits for small-cell deployments, despite significant variability in the requisite interfaces for each solution.

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